

Repeating Crossbow Optimization

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Abstract

The geometry and other properties of a repeating crossbow was optimized in order to maximize the output power. This article focuses mostly on the geometry of the 3-bar mechanism that distinguishes repeating crossbows from traditional crossbows but describes a model set up to be scaled for additional optimization with greater dimensionality. An optimization method was chosen that fits the problem and code is provided to demonstrate how this optimization was done to receive the reported results. While the results did not improve upon existing repeating crossbow power output, with adjusted constraints, it is believed that a fully optimized design can be found based on this work.

Introduction

Throughout history, war has been a major driving force for innovation and engineering. Projectile weaponry was one of the first major revolutions known of that progressed ancient warfare. Many ideas were tested to try and perfect the ancient projectile weapon. However, these weapons were often either bulky and slow to operate, taking much time and skill to learn to use, or, if built for ease of use, the strength and effectiveness were decreased. One example of this is the crossbow. Crossbows improved upon the traditional bow because of the increased speed of flight of the projectile. The crossbow also took slightly less skill due to their point-and-shoot design. However, a main drawback of the crossbow was its lengthy load, cock, and fire time. In order to improve this, the repeating crossbow was developed.

The repeating crossbow is a Chinese invention, which basically added a three-bar mechanism on top of a crossbow, which held multiple projectiles and allowed the user to load, cock, and fire the weapon much faster. Historically, an archer operating a repeating crossbow could fire at a rate of about one bolt per second, as opposed to a traditional crossbow's rate of less than 10 bolts per minute. Unfortunately, the tradeoff mentioned before still applies here. While able to fire faster than any other ancient bow, the repeating crossbow did not produce anywhere near the same amount of force or accuracy its predecessors did. However, could this be changed? Many more tools are available for modern engineers than when the repeating crossbow was developed. Therefore, our goal was to optimize the power output of a repeating crossbow using modern optimization techniques.

Methods

a. Model

The initial step to this optimization was to develop a model accurate enough to define what can be changed to increase the power of the crossbow. Small steps were taken while developing this model to ensure accuracy, but resulted in insufficient time to fully complete the optimization desired. Therefore, the current results are outlined, but future development is needed and steps to do so are also outlined at the end of this report.

Specifically, in order to simplify the model, it was broken into two main areas. First is the 3-bar mechanism on top of the crossbow. This was the main area of focus for the

optimization as it is what initially weakened the crossbow, as stated above. The 3-bar mechanism consists of a lever, which the user pumped back and forth. The forward motion of the lever moves the entire magazine forward where the string is then caught in a notch. Once the string is caught, the user pulls the lever all the way back, where a nub on the stock pushes the string up into its normal slot, firing the crossbow. Pushing the lever forward catches the string again and on the back stroke a new bolt falls into place from the magazine. The basic model of this mechanism is laid out below in Figure 1. The lever arm is made up of the sum of the lengths of r_2 and r_4 . The magazine is approximated as r_3 .

Figure 1 (a) upper: repeating crossbow with 3-bar mechanism in loading position; middle: repeating crossbow with 3-bar mechanism in firing position; bottom: repeating crossbow with 3-bar mechanism in fired position (b) simplified model of 3-bar mechanism

The position of the 3-bar mechanism was solved using kinematic equations. It is important to note that the diagram provided in Figure 1(b) shows r_3 as a constant length but what worked best for this system was solving for the length of r_3 given an input angle θ_2 . This more closely approximated what is observed when the repeating crossbow is operated. The difference between r_3 at its starting position and its end position was used as the distance K was pulled. This distance allowed us to calculate

the force the bow exerted on the mechanism. This then was modified based on the mechanical advantage produced by the mechanism and compared to what would be reasonable for a user to consistently output.

It should also be noted that in this iteration of the project, integrals were not used to determine the actual power. Instead, the force experienced as the lever is fully pulled back was used as an approximation for the entire force, and then power was calculated. It was decided that a configuration that would do well under this approximation would also do well in a more detailed model. This approach was taken since the optimal set up of the crossbow was more of a focus than the actual power of the crossbow itself.

The second main area was the bow portion of the crossbow. More work needs to be done in this area, but it was begun by approximating the resistance of the bow string as a spring (spring constant K in Figure 1) and allowing the optimization algorithm to adjust it as well.

b. Optimization

The problem statement that was optimized is as follows.

Maximize: Power = Force*Velocity

With Respect To: $r_1, r_2, r_4, \theta_2, K$

Subject To:

- Arc Length
 $g_1 = (\text{arc length point A in Figure 1 travels}) - (\text{arm length of average crossbow operator})$
- Weight
 $g_2 = (\text{total weight of crossbow}) - (\text{maximum weight of usable crossbow})$
- Force
 $g_3 = (\text{force operator inputs}) - (\text{plausible operator input force})$
- Construction Constraints
Lower link length bounds were set to be a plausible length so the crossbow can still be constructed.
- Speed
Velocity determining power output is determined by the maximum speed crossbow operator's arm can move back and forth to load and fire.

A gradient-based optimization algorithm was initially chosen because of its simplicity and accessibility. The constrained optimizer function, `fmincon`, from MATLAB's optimization toolbox was used. In order to actually optimize, the objective power function was made negative. This will be how the results and plots will be presented.

It was found that results would vary based on initial values for design variables, so it was expected that there were multiple optima. Because of this, the optimization method was

switched to a particle swarm optimization in order to assure a global optimum would be found. This method worked for this problem due to the inexpensive nature of evaluating the model as well as its low dimensionality. It was also determined that a gradient-free method would be preferable due to the discontinuities in the function, as can be seen in Figure 2 in the results section. Once the general area for each optimum was found using the gradient free method, a gradient based method was used to hone in on the more exact answer.

If additional questions arise about the setup of the equations or optimization, the code implemented can be accessed at <https://github.com/Dasay3/Repeating-Crossbow.git>.

Results

As mentioned above and shown in Figure 2, two optima were found for this problem because of how the constraints were set up. The optima are shown in table 1.

Figure 2: Different angles of plot showing two optima of function. However, this is just the output with respect to two design variables and does not fully represent the entire function.

Table 1: results for two optimums

	1st Optimum (Best)	2nd Optimum
r_1 (cm)	5	5
r_2 (cm)	5	7.18
r_4 (cm)	24.3	19.7
theta_2 (degree)	48	30
K (N/cm)	2076	5.755x10 ⁸
Power (N*cm/sec)	8.77x10 ⁵	5.54x10 ⁵

Discussion

Our results show that there are actually two optimums in the system, and which one is best depends on the constraints that are chosen. Our constraints were chosen on what we thought was reasonable for construction and usage, but when we looked at a real repeating crossbow we discovered that it violated them. In fact, the real repeating crossbow was better than this optimized result, which means that in the future, the constraints of this problem need to be selected more carefully.

Another observation from these results is that r_1 is always pushed to the lower bound set for it and r_2 was as well in one case. This was not an expected result since these both affect the displacement of K and a larger displacement should increase power. There potentially is an error in the calculations somewhere in the model which will need to be examined more thoroughly.

It should also be noted that the model is incomplete. Multiple design variables and constraints that will greatly affect the solution were left out. However, the problem was set up so that these could be easily added in later. These future additions are included below.

Design Variables

- Bow sizing - This will include length, width, and other parameters of the bow.
- Bow position - Friction between the string and channel is mainly a problem because of the angle that the string has to be at due to the bow position. Therefore, changing the position of the bow can decrease friction and increase power.

- Material properties - Materials were more limited in ancient times when this weapon was designed, so finding the right material to optimize weight and strength will be important.

Constraints:

- Friction - Friction is a significant issue between string and the channel it slides through.
- Weight - Weight was considered and limited for the 3-bar mechanism links, but should also be considered for the entire crossbow.
- Internal stresses - When material properties are added as design variables, the internal stresses will be a large factor in what materials are chosen for the mechanism link as well as the bow since these are areas of high stress during firing.
- Speed - Should be found based off of expected forces

Overall, an effective, scalable model was created for this problem and a sufficient optimization method was chosen. Since the optima found were not any better than the original design, there is still room for future development as described above.

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